

TEACHERS' TEACHING PROFICIENCY AND GRADE 7 LEARNER'S ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN THE KEY LEARNING AREAS IN THE 4th CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON PROVINCE: BASIS FOR TEACHERS' CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

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This study aimed to assess the teacher's teaching proficiency of the public secondary school and the grade 7 learner's academic performance in the 4th Congressional District of Quezon Province. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed to collect data using a survey questionnaire as the primary instrument. The study included school head and public secondary school teachers from the aforementioned district as respondents, selected through random sampling. The study utilized the mean to describe the level of teachers' teaching proficiency, including communication and interpersonal skills, organization and planning, classroom management, assessment and coaching, collaboration and teamwork, and flexibility and adaptability. Additionally, the mean was used to describe the grade 7 learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was employed to determine any significant relationships between teachers' teaching proficiency and grade 7 learners' academic performance. The primary research question focused on assessing teachers' teaching proficiency and grade 7 learners' academic performance in the 4th Congressional District of Quezon Province. The null hypothesis, suggesting no relationship between teachers' teaching proficiency and grade 7 learners' academic performance, was rejected based on the study's findings. Based on this finding, the researcher proposed a Teacher's Continuing Professional Development Plan. As a result of this study, several recommendations are proposed: Establish a robust monitoring and evaluation system to continually assess teachers' teaching proficiency and the grade 7

learner's academic performance in the district, allocate resources to develop comprehensive teacher training programs that target the enhancement of teaching proficiency, subject knowledge updates, and pedagogical skill development, ensure accessibility of these programs to teachers within the 4th Congressional District of Quezon Province, promote regular team meetings among teachers for sharing best practices, addressing challenges, and brainstorming innovative teaching strategies, encourage cross-grade and cross-subject collaborations to foster interdisciplinary learning and a sense of unity among teaching staff, allocate resources and time for teachers' professional development activities, offer financial assistance for attending relevant conferences or facilitate in-house training sessions conducted by field experts, encourage knowledge-sharing among teachers through peer-to-peer training sessions and suggest that future researchers investigating teacher proficiency utilize the same instrument employed in this study, thus ensuring consistency and comparability of findings.

Keywords: *Teaching Proficiency, Academic Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines' poor performance in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) has underscored the urgent need for educational reform. Despite the introduction of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, persistent challenges persist within the nation's educational landscape. As the Philippine educational system transitions towards a curriculum tailored to 21st-century learning, emphasis is placed on fostering communication skills, higher-order thinking, and problem-solving abilities among learners.

In navigating these evolving educational demands, competence, as defined by Varvel (2013), emerges as a pivotal factor. This blend of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and abilities is essential for educators striving to meet the needs of contemporary education. However, a significant obstacle lies in the insufficient training of educators in essential instructional communication skills, as highlighted by Maragha (2024).

DepEd Order No. 8 (s. 2015) underscores the critical role of classroom assessment in the K to 12 Basic Education Program, drawing upon Vygotsky's zone of proximal development. Despite this directive, many teachers in the Philippines tend to favor mechanistic assessment processes over embracing formative assessment as a pedagogical strategy. To address this, research has identified varying levels of teacher proficiency in formative assessment, offering a structured pathway for professional development aligned with educational objectives.

Moreover, recent studies have explored the relationship between teacher competence and 21st-century skills. By examining the influence of each dimension on teacher competence, these studies provide insights into predictive factors in 21st-century teachers' skills in teaching. For instance, a study involving 242 secondary school teachers in Peninsular Malaysia reveals a robust and positive relationship between professional

competence and 21st-century skills. The dimensions of teacher competence, including personal characteristics, pedagogy, professional development, information and communication technology (ICT) skills, as well as school management and development, contribute significantly to 21st-century skills.

These findings are aligned with the broader advocacy to promote academic excellence and quality education, particularly within the Schools Division of Quezon Province. By recognizing and addressing teaching skills, this initiative aims to enhance educational outcomes and foster academic success in the Philippines.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to establish a baseline for the teachers' continuing professional development plan by relating the teachers' teaching proficiency to the grade 7 learner's academic performance in the 4th Congressional District of Quezon Province.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following subproblems:

1. What is the level of the teachers' teaching proficiency in terms of the following domains?
 - 1.1. Communication and Interpersonal Skills
 - 1.2. Organization and Planning
 - 1.3. Classroom Management
 - 1.4. Assessment and Coaching
 - 1.5. Collaboration and Teamwork
 - 1.6. Flexibility and Adaptability
2. What is the level of grade 7 learner's academic performance in the following key learning areas?
 - 2.1. English
 - 2.2. Mathematics
 - 2.3. Science
3. Is there a significant relationship in the grade 7 learner's academic performance in the following key learning areas?
 - 3.1. English
 - 3.2. Mathematics
 - 2.3. Science
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of the teachers' teaching proficiency and the grade 7 learner's academic performance in the key learning areas?
 - 4.1. Communication and Interpersonal Skills
 - 4.2. Organization and Planning
 - 4.3. Classroom Management
 - 4.4. Assessment and Coaching
 - 4.5. Collaboration and Teamwork
 - 4.6. Flexibility and Adaptability
5. What Teachers' Continuing Professional Development Plan could be made from the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design in order to determine the level of teachers' teaching proficiency and grade 7 learner's academic performance in the public secondary high schools in the 4th Congressional District of Quezon Province for the School Year 2022 – 2023, as input for the Proposed Teachers' Continuing Professional Development Plan. In addition, the descriptive-correlational research method was utilized in the study. To ascertain the connection between teacher's teaching proficiency and learner's academic performance. A quantitative approach was used to quantify data and generalize results from a sample population of interest. Structured information was formulated through the questionnaire for analysis and interpretation.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the public secondary high schools in the 4th Congressional District of Quezon. The district consists of municipalities in the Tayabas Isthmus and Alabat Island, namely Alabat, Atimonan, Calauag, Guinayangan, Gumaca, Lopez, Perez, Plaridel, Quezon and Tagkawayan.

A questionnaire was given to the respondents, and the researcher will also collect data on how the grade 7 learners performed in the 1st and 2nd quarters of the School Year 2022 - 2023 in the subject of English, Mathematics, and Science 2022 – 2023. The 4th Congressional District in the Province of Quezon was chosen by the researcher due to a strategic combination of professional alignment and a dedication to community engagement. First off, the researcher's current position with the district guarantees direct access to local networks, insights, and potentially useful data sources, which promotes a more complex comprehension of the state of education. This familiarity can make the research study more thorough and contextually successful.

Moreover, the researcher's desire to contribute to the community and support fellow teachers adds a commendable dimension to the research endeavor. By conducting the study in a location where they are already employed, the researcher aims not only to advance academic knowledge but also to directly impact and enhance the educational experiences of colleagues. This dual purpose of contributing to both academia and the immediate professional community reinforces the relevance and potential positive outcomes of the research. The unique combination of professional proximity and a commitment to community welfare makes the 4th Congressional District of Quezon Province, an apt and meaningful choice for the research focus.

Research Population and Sample

Random sampling was utilized in this study to determine the number of respondents and the availability of the respondents in this study.

The following are the numbers of research respondents in this study.

Table No. 1. Distribution of Respondents from 4th Congressional District of Quezon Province

District	Name of School	School Size	Number of Respondents			
			School Head	Co-Teachers	Teachers	Total
Alabat	Alabat National High School	Large	1	3	3	7
	RT Camacho Integrated School	Medium	1	3	3	7
Atimonan	Atimonan National Comprehensive High School	Large	1	3	3	7
	Malinao Integrated National High School	Medium	1	3	3	7
	San Rafael National High School	Small	1	3	3	7
Calauag	Calauag National High School	Large	1	3	3	7
	Lagay National High School	Medium	1	3	3	7
	Apad National High School	Small	1	3	3	7
Guinayangan	Guinayangan National High School	Large	1	3	3	7
	Nabangka National High School	Medium	1	3	3	7
	Sta. Cruz National High School	Small	1	3	3	7
Gumaca	Gumaca National High School	Large	1	3	3	7
	Panikihan National High School	Medium	1	3	3	7

	Villa Perez National High School	Small	1	3	3	7
Lopez	Lopez National Comprehensive High School	Large	1	3	3	7
	Magallanes National High School	Medium	1	3	3	7
	Pamampangin National High School	Small	1	3	3	7
Perez	Perez National High School	Large	1	3	3	7
	Severo Tejada Integrated School	Medium	1	3	3	7
Plaridel	Concepcion National High School	Large	1	3	3	7
Quezon	Cesar Tan Memorial National High School	Large	1	3	3	7
	Cometa National High School	Medium	1	3	3	7
	Pablo D. Maningas National High School	Small	1	3	3	7
Tagkawayan	Tagkawayan National High School	Large	1	3	3	7
	Bagong Silang National High School	Medium	1	3	3	7
	Kinatakutan National High School	Small	1	3	3	7
Total			26	78	78	182

Data Gathering Procedure

The following procedures were used in gathering data relative to the conduct of the study. For the research process, the following procedures were undertaken. the

researcher secured permission from the different persons in authority to allow the researcher to conduct the study. The researcher sent letters to Schools Division Superintendent and public secondary school principals. As soon as the request was approved, the researcher sent the Google Link to every school to fill out the data in the instruments. Upon retrieval, the researcher will review each instrument to ensure all the items are properly answered. Then the data were tallied, computed, analyzed, and interpreted.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After administering and retrieving the accomplished questionnaire, data was categorized, organized, and statistically treated using the following statistical tools:

To interpret the weighted mean of questions 1 and 2, the following continuum was used:

Assigned Value	Scale Range	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25 – 4.00	Highly Proficient	HP
3	2.50 – 3.24	Proficient	P
2	1.75 – 2.49	Basic	B
1	1.00 – 1.75	Below Basic	BB

Pearson's Product Moment of Correlation was used to resolve sub-problem 3 and 4.

The following continuum was used to interpret Pearson's Product Moment of Correlation results:

Size of Correlation:

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
± 1.00	Perfectly positive/ negative correlation
$\pm 0.90 - 0.99$	Very high positive/ negative correlation
$\pm 0.70 - 0.89$	High positive/ negative correlation
$\pm 0.50 - 0.69$	Moderately positive/ negative correlation
$\pm 0.30 - 0.49$	Low positive/ negative correlation
$\pm 0.01 - 0.29$	Negligible correlation
0.00	No correlation at all

The following scale and corresponding description were used to interpret the performance of the grade 7 learners:

Grading Scale	Description
90-100 %	Outstanding
85-89 %	Very Satisfactory
80-84 %	Satisfactory
75-79 %	Fairly Satisfactory
75 % below	Did Not Meet Expectations

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I. Level of Teachers' Teaching Proficiency

Table 2. Teachers' Teaching Proficiency Overall Mean Ratings for Communication and Interpersonal Skills.

Rater	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)	Qualitative Description
Principal	3.08	0.29	Proficient
Co-Teacher	3.07	0.25	Proficient
Teacher (self)	3.11	0.40	Proficient
Overall	3.09	0.31	Proficient

Table 2 provides an overview of the mean distribution of teachers' teaching proficiency in communication and interpersonal skills, with all respondents self-reporting as 'Proficient.' The results shed light on both strengths and areas for improvement. Notably, the highest mean score of 3.18 is attributed to the indicator "Builds strong interpersonal relationships with other people." This suggests that the teacher excels in fostering positive connections and relationships within the educational environment.

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 2.99 is associated with the indicator "Seeks out and listens to others who have contrary opinions." This indicates a potential area for enhancement, suggesting that the teacher could focus on actively seeking diverse viewpoints and listening attentively to individuals with differing opinions.

The ratings from self-assessment, principal evaluation, and co-teacher feedback consistently fall within the 'Proficient' range. This alignment in perceptions signifies a shared understanding of the teachers' proficiency among different stakeholders.

In summary, these findings provide valuable insights for professional development. The teacher can capitalize on their strength in building interpersonal relationships while dedicating efforts to improve the skill of actively seeking and listening to diverse opinions. Collaborative efforts involving self-reflection, guidance from the principal, and insights

from co-teachers can contribute to a holistic approach for continuous improvement in communication and interpersonal skills.

The study Xie and Derakhshan (2021) and Hargie (2021) contribute insights into the predictive nature of teacher-learner relationships in shaping emotions, stressing the relevance of interpersonal communication skills for teaching success. Stamatis (2013) further highlights the importance of teachers' associations in enhancing their work through communication, acknowledging the role of personality and willingness to learn. These studies collectively underscore the crucial role of communication in fostering positive relationships and supporting informed decision-making in the educational setting.

Table 3. Teachers' Teaching Proficiency Overall Mean Ratings in Terms of Organization and Planning

Rater	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)	Qualitative Description
Principal	3.08	0.29	Proficient
Co-Teacher	3.07	0.25	Proficient
Teacher (self)	3.11	0.40	Proficient
Overall	3.09	0.31	Proficient

Table 3 presents the teachers' organizational and planning proficiency, considering self-assessment, principal's ratings, and co-teacher feedback. Notably, the teacher exhibits a commendable proficiency in making decisions on time, with all evaluations converging on a highly proficient mean of 3.25. This reflects a strong ability to navigate time constraints effectively. Additionally, the teachers' knack for anticipating negative and positive consequences is a standout strength, garnering a highly proficient mean of 3.48, especially highlighted by the principal's rating.

However, areas for improvement are identified, particularly in the competency of monitoring information for on-going projects and prioritizing tasks. While proficient, these proficiencies could benefit from focused attention and potential professional development initiatives.

Furthermore, the teachers' obtaining and using relevant information to identify problems, knowing when expert knowledge is needed, and developing efficient plans and schedules is acknowledged, with mean scores in the proficient range. Collaboratively, the teacher demonstrates proficiency in organizing individuals around tasks, indicating a potential for effective collaborative planning.

The findings of the study highlight a balanced perspective on teachers' organizational and planning skills, emphasizing the importance of recognizing and affirming these proficiencies. This acknowledgment not only serves to affirm strengths but also provides a strategic roadmap for targeted professional development, ensuring continuous growth and effectiveness in organizational and planning capacities.

In relation to these findings, Ambag's study (2015) aligns with the emphasis on planning and assessment outlined in the summary. Ambag describes a process involving planning, assessing, and reporting learner's outcomes. This process emphasizes the alignment of assessment and planning activities to ensure appropriate teaching-learning activities based on learner's current knowledge and learning levels. The integration of formative assessment procedures into teaching activities, along with hands-on experiences for learners, supports the development of creativity and innovation in alternative teaching approaches. Ambag's insights reinforce the importance of intentional planning and assessment, contributing to the overall enhancement of organizational and planning skills among educators.

Table 4. Teachers' Teaching Proficiency Overall Mean Ratings in Terms of Classroom Management

Rater	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)	Qualitative Description
Principal	3.05	0.11	Proficient
Co-Teacher	3.06	0.17	Proficient
Teacher (self)	3.24	0.43	Proficient
Overall	3.12	0.24	Proficient

Table 4 presents the teachers' classroom management proficiency, reflecting self-assessment, principal evaluations, and co-teacher perspectives. The teacher demonstrates proficiency in encouraging learner expression and discussions, earning a highly proficient mean of 3.24. This aligns with a collaborative learning approach, as indicated by the mean of 3.27, showcasing effective learning management to promote teamwork among learners. Notably, the teachers' adeptness in creating a physical environment conducive to learning, with a highly proficient mean of 3.26, is recognized across evaluations.

In terms of classroom structure management, a highly proficient mean of 3.31 is reported, although the principal's rating slightly differs, suggesting a potential area for communication and clarification. The teacher excels in providing activities for joyful learning, focusing on real and lively practice, and allowing learners to choose activities based on their interests and abilities, all achieving proficient mean scores.

Moreover, the teacher exhibits effective behavior management skills, maintaining a positive environment with a mean of 3.08. It is noteworthy that all ratings consistently fall within the 'Proficient' and 'Highly Proficient' categories, indicating a shared understanding among stakeholders.

In conclusion, the findings underscore the teachers' ability to foster an engaging and collaborative classroom environment, emphasizing learner expression and varied learning experiences. The table serves as a valuable tool for recognizing strengths, addressing potential areas for improvement, and fostering continued excellence in classroom management.

As mentioned by Sultan (2018), maintaining order in the classroom and fostering positive relationships with learners can boost their confidence, increase interest in academic subjects, and improve their overall performance and achievements. Several studies have linked factors like teacher warmth, classroom order, and emotional support to learner success and performance. In essence, a well-structured and supportive classroom environment plays a significant role in positively influencing learner's attitudes and academic outcomes.

Table 5. Teachers' Teaching Proficiency Overall Mean Ratings in Terms of Assessment and Coaching

Rater	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)	Qualitative Description
Principal	3.05	0.11	Proficient
Co-Teacher	3.06	0.17	Proficient
Teacher (self)	3.24	0.43	Proficient
Overall	3.12	0.24	Proficient

Table 5 presents the teachers' proficiency in assessment and coaching, incorporating self-assessment, principal evaluations, and co-teacher feedback. The teacher demonstrates proficiency in establishing a conducive learning environment, although there is a noticeable divergence in ratings, especially with the principal's assessment being lower. This suggests a potential area for communication and collaborative efforts to align expectations and strategies for creating an optimal learning climate.

In terms of evaluating learning outcomes and re-diagnosing learning needs, the teacher maintains proficiency, emphasizing a sense of progress towards educational goals. Additionally, the teacher recognizes the pivotal role of teacher quality in learner success, receiving a proficient mean rating of 3.11.

Mentoring learners in content and skills difficulties stands out as a highly proficient competency, underscoring the teachers' ability to provide valuable support to learners. The teacher also excels in coaching learners through various activities and decisions, exhibiting proficiency in adapting coaching approaches to different situations.

Encouraging learners to complete tasks through questioning, while proficient, indicates a potential area for enhancement. The teachers' adaptability in coaching and mentoring, particularly when learners can independently make decisions, receives proficient mean ratings.

In essence, this table offers a nuanced understanding of the teachers' strengths in assessment and coaching, pinpointing areas for refinement and growth. The collaborative nature of the evaluation process involving self-assessment, principal, and co-teacher perspectives ensures a holistic approach to professional development, facilitating ongoing improvements in teaching proficiency.

Based on Magno (2018) emphasizes the importance of aligning assessment and planning activities in education. It emphasizes the use of assessment data to plan and modify teaching-learning plans, integrating assessment procedures into the execution of activities. Teachers must promptly communicate learner's progress to parents, superiors, and themselves, and employ various assessment strategies for monitoring and evaluating learning. Regular monitoring and feedback on learner's understanding of content are also crucial. This highlights the interconnectedness of assessment, planning, and effective communication in the educational process.

Table 6. Teachers' Teaching Proficiency Overall Mean Ratings in Terms of Collaboration and Teamwork

Rater	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)	Qualitative Description
Principal	2.26	0.50	Proficient
Co-Teacher	3.12	0.28	Proficient
Teacher (self)	3.17	0.42	Proficient
Overall	3.18	0.40	Proficient

Table 6 provides a comprehensive overview of the teachers' proficiency in collaboration and teamwork, revealing valuable insights from self-assessment, principal evaluations, and co-teacher feedback. A standout strength is evident in the teachers' Assists the team in acquiring the resources and support it needs to accomplish its goals proficient mean of 3.20. This underscores the teachers' capability to navigate logistical challenges and foster an environment conducive to effective teamwork.

Conversely, an area for potential improvement lies in the indicator "Provides team members with a clear vision of what is to be accomplished by the team," which received a proficient mean of 2.86. This suggests a need for refining the communication of overarching goals, setting expectations, and inspiring team members toward a shared vision. Clarity in vision is fundamental for team alignment and motivation.

The implications of these findings are noteworthy. The teachers' strength in resource facilitation is a valuable asset that can be leveraged to further enhance collaborative efforts. On the other hand, recognizing the need for improvement in articulating a clear vision emphasizes the importance of effective communication in fostering cohesive teamwork.

Moving forward, a strategic focus on professional development could be considered, particularly in areas related to vision communication. Workshops or training sessions on effective communication strategies and leadership in collaborative settings could provide valuable tools for the teacher to enhance this aspect of their collaborative skill set.

The study by Hargreaves (2021) highlights complexities beyond the obvious advantages of teacher collaboration and offers a nuanced analysis of collaboration and

teamwork proficiency. It delves into ideas like professional capital, collaborative professionalism, and contrived collegiality, illuminating the complexities of teamwork. Furthermore, Le, Janssen, and Wubbels (2018) emphasize how important it is for teachers in Sweden to collaborate and work as a team in order to support the transition to research-based education. Their focus on context-specific development, collaborative learning communities, and bottom-up perspectives highlights the importance of multiple levels of engagement in schools. This thorough grasp of collaboration and teamwork proficiency provides a road map for focused professional development that builds on current competencies and targets particular areas in need of improvement. In the end, this strategy helps to foster the development of a more efficient and motivated collaborative teaching environment

Table 7. Teachers' Teaching Competencies in Overall Mean Ratings Terms of Flexibility and Adaptability

Rater	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)	Qualitative Description
Principal	3.15	0.39	Proficient
Co-Teacher	3.15	0.34	Proficient
Teacher (self)	3.06	0.36	Proficient
Overall	3.12	0.36	Proficient

Table 7 presents the teachers' proficiency in flexibility and adaptability. A notable strength emerges in the teachers' ability to encourage strong feedback mechanisms, as reflected in the highly proficient mean of 3.30. This signifies a commendable commitment to fostering open communication and continuous improvement, crucial elements in adapting to the dynamic demands of the educational environment.

On the other hand, the indicator "Look for positive ways to make changes" stands as an area with potential for improvement, registering a proficient mean of 3.08. Although still within the proficient range, this suggests an opportunity for the teacher to cultivate a more proactive attitude towards change, recognizing it as an avenue for positive growth and advancement in teaching methodologies.

The implications of these findings are multifaceted. Leveraging the strength in fostering a culture of strong feedback is crucial for continuous improvement and aligning teaching practices with evolving educational needs. Simultaneously, recognizing the room for improvement in proactively seeking positive changes underscores the importance of embracing change as an inherent aspect of professional development.

Strategically, targeted professional development activities could focus on change management strategies and instilling a positive outlook towards change. This might involve workshops or training sessions dedicated to equipping the teacher with the mindset and tools needed to navigate and welcome change as an opportunity for enhancement.

In conclusion, the nuanced analysis of flexibility and adaptability proficiency highlights the teachers' existing strengths and areas for growth. By capitalizing on feedback mechanisms and proactively embracing change, the teacher can further enhance their adaptability, contributing to a teaching approach that is not only proficient but also resilient and responsive to the evolving landscape of education.

On the other hand, Jadama (2019) emphasizes the importance of teachers' deep understanding of their subject matter in delivering effective content. This knowledge instills confidence in teachers, enabling them to select suitable teaching strategies and skills for their learners. Teachers with a strong command of the subject matter can provide detailed explanations to learners, enhancing their learning experience. The expertise and up-to-date knowledge positively impact the teaching-learning process, allowing learners to practice and apply knowledge in their daily activities. Overall, the paragraph emphasizes the significance of teachers' deep subject knowledge in facilitating effective teaching and meaningful learning experiences.

Part II. Level of Grade 7 Learner's Academic Performance

Table 8. Grade 7 Learner's Academic Performance in the 1st and 2nd Quarter

Key Subject Areas	First Quarter			Second Quarter			Overall Performance	
	Mean Percentage	Std. Deviation	Description	Mean Percentage	Std. Deviation	Description	Mean Percentage	Description
English	86.23	1.42	Very Satisfactory	86.18	1.28	Very Satisfactory	86.21	Very Satisfactory
Mathematics	86.24	1.15	Very Satisfactory	85.84	1.41	Very Satisfactory	86.04	Very Satisfactory
Science	86.10	0.77	Very Satisfactory	86.03	0.84	Very Satisfactory	86.07	Very Satisfactory
Overall Performance	86.19	1.11	Very Satisfactory	86.02	1.18	Very Satisfactory	86.11	Very Satisfactory

Legend: Outstanding 90-100, Very Satisfactory 85-89, Satisfactory 80-84, Fairly Satisfactory 75-79, Did Not Meet the Expectation – 75 below

The table 8 provided outlines the academic performance of a learner across two semesters in three subjects: English, Mathematics, and Science. The data illustrates a consistent and commendable performance throughout both semesters. In the first semester, the mean scores for English, Mathematics, and Science were 86.23, 86.24, and 86.10, respectively, with relatively low standard deviations, suggesting a tight distribution of scores around the mean. Similarly, in the second semester, the mean scores for these subjects remained consistently high, with slight fluctuations: 86.18 for English, 85.84 for Mathematics, and 86.03 for Science, accompanied by slightly increased standard deviations. Despite these minor variations, all scores remained within the "Very Satisfactory" range, indicating a strong and stable performance. The overall performance, considering both semesters, showcased mean scores of 86.21 for English, 86.04 for Mathematics, and 86.07 for Science, emphasizing the learner's consistently high academic achievement across the board.

The data presented reflects a learner consistently achieving high marks in English, Mathematics, and Science across two semesters. The mean scores consistently fall within the "Very Satisfactory" range, indicating a strong grasp of the subjects. However, there are slight decreases in mean scores for Mathematics in the second semester compared to the first.

While the learner's overall performance remains commendable and "Very Satisfactory," the minor decrease in Mathematics scores from the first to the second semester might suggest a need for focused attention or extra support in that subject area. It could be beneficial for the learner to engage in additional practice, seek clarification on challenging concepts, or even consider supplemental tutoring to maintain or improve their performance in Mathematics. This targeted effort could help ensure sustained high performance across all subjects.

Similar trends in academic performance, with slight fluctuations across semesters, are common and have been observed in various studies on learner achievement. Consistency in high scores across subjects, as seen in this case, often indicates a strong understanding and consistent effort by the learner. However, fluctuations in performance between semesters, particularly in a specific subject like Mathematics, have been noted in educational research.

Studies often highlight that learners might encounter challenges in particular subjects due to various factors such as the complexity of concepts, teaching methodologies, or personal learning styles. These fluctuations may not necessarily indicate a lack of understanding but might reflect variations in teaching methods, different topics covered, or individual learning curves.

Implications from such findings stress the importance of continuous support and tailored strategies to maintain consistent academic excellence. Educators often emphasize the significance of identifying and addressing weaker areas promptly to prevent further decline in performance. This could involve personalized learning plans, targeted interventions, or extra support sessions aimed at specific subjects where learners show a decline in performance over time.

Ambag (2015) highlights the importance of various elements in the teaching-learning process to help learners achieve high standards of learning and understand curricular goals. These elements include the teacher's knowledge of the subject matter, teaching approaches, instructional materials, and learning resources. Learners are expected to possess fundamental literacy, communication, numeracy, and critical thinking skills. Teachers should communicate learning goals, manage instructional time effectively, and choose appropriate teaching methods, activities, and materials. The interconnectedness of these elements is crucial for achieving comprehensive learner learning outcomes.

Part III. Correlation of Key Learning Areas per Quarter

Table 9. Test for Correlation of the Key Learning Areas in the 1st Quarter

Areas		N	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	Int	Discussion
English	Mathematics	78	.426**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Science		-.053	.647	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Mathematics	English	78	.426**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Science		.625**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Science	English	78	-.053	.647	Not Significant	Accept
	Mathematics		.625**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 9 provided correlation table examines the relationships between learner’s academic performances in three subjects—English, Mathematics, and Science—specifically during the 1st quarter. The correlation coefficients reveal interesting insights into the connections between these subjects.

There is a moderate positive correlation (Pearson Correlation coefficient of .426) between English and Mathematics. This indicates that, during this period, there was a discernible, though not exceedingly strong, relationship between performances in these two subjects. The statistical significance, denoted by the Sig. value of .000, confirms that this correlation is statistically meaningful.

Conversely, the correlation between English and Science appears negligible, with a very weak negative correlation (Pearson Correlation coefficient of -.053) and a non-significant p-value of .647. This implies that, during this quarter, there was no notable relationship between the academic performances in English and Science among the pupils.

In contrast, Mathematics and Science display a notably stronger positive correlation (Pearson Correlation coefficient of .625**), signifying a substantial and statistically significant relationship between the performances in these two subjects during this specific period.

These findings suggest that while Mathematics and Science performances were closely linked during the first quarter, the relationship between English and Science performance was insignificant. This may indicate differing influences or learning patterns in these subjects during this particular timeframe for these learners. Understanding these correlations can aid educators in tailoring teaching strategies to potentially strengthen interrelated subjects or address specific areas that show weaker connections among learner’s academic performances.

The review paper examines research conducted Vermunt, J. D., & Vermetten, Y. J. (2004). over the past decade on patterns in student learning, particularly in higher education contexts. It focuses on studies utilizing the Inventory of Learning Styles (ILS) and integrative learning theories, which assess various aspects of student learning such as cognitive and metacognitive strategies, conceptions of learning, and learning orientations. The review covers topics including theoretical frameworks, internal structures of learning strategies, developments in learning patterns over students' educational careers, the influence of personal and contextual factors on learning, relationships between learning patterns and academic outcomes, and the importance of process-oriented instruction. Overall, the paper provides insights into how understanding different learning patterns can inform instructional practices and support student academic performance.

Table 10. Test for Correlation of the Key Learning Areas in the 2nd Quarter

Key Learning Areas		N	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	Int	Discussion
English	Mathematics	78	.397**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Science		.206	.070	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Mathematics	English	78	.397**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Science		.315**	.005	Significant	Reject Ho
Science	English	78	.206	.070	Not Significant	Accept
	Mathematics		.315**	.005	Significant	Reject Ho

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 10 shows the correlation analysis for learner's academic performance in the second quarter across three subjects—English, Mathematics, and Science—reveals distinct patterns of relationships between these subjects.

There is a moderate positive correlation (Pearson Correlation coefficient of .397**) between English and Mathematics, indicating a significant relationship between performances in these subjects during this quarter. This correlation, consistent with the previous quarter, remains statistically meaningful, suggesting a consistent association between achievements in English and Mathematics.

In contrast, the correlation between English and Science remains weak (Pearson Correlation coefficient of .206) during this quarter, similar to the previous analysis. The p-value of .070 indicates that this correlation lacks statistical significance, implying that there isn't a robust relationship between English and Science performances for these learners during this period.

Conversely, Mathematics and Science show a moderate positive correlation (Pearson Correlation coefficient of .315), indicating a notable relationship between the

performances in these subjects. This correlation is statistically significant, indicating a consistent association between Mathematics and Science achievements during this specific quarter.

These findings mirror those from the previous quarter, emphasizing the consistent association between Mathematics and both English and Science performances. However, the correlation between English and Science remains relatively weak and non-significant. Educators can leverage these insights to tailor instructional strategies, potentially strengthening connections between subjects or focusing on areas that exhibit weaker relationships in learner’s academic performances during this timeframe.

The research conducted by Mushtaq, I., & Khan, S. N. (2012) focuses on investigating factors that influence college students' performance in intermediate examinations, particularly examining their approach to communication, access to learning facilities, availability of proper guidance, and levels of family stress. These factors are identified as crucial elements shaping students' academic outcomes. Effective communication skills are highlighted as essential, as students who can effectively articulate their thoughts and engage in class discussions tend to have a deeper understanding of course materials, which positively impacts their exam performance. Additionally, access to learning resources such as libraries, laboratories, and study materials is noted as critical for facilitating learning and comprehension. Proper guidance from teachers and mentors is emphasized as important for supporting students' academic journey, providing them with clear instructions, feedback, and mentorship to navigate challenges effectively. Conversely, family stressors such as financial difficulties or personal conflicts are recognized as potential barriers to academic success, as they can contribute to increased anxiety, distraction, and decreased motivation among students. Addressing these factors comprehensively through support systems, resources, and interventions is essential for promoting students' academic performance and overall well-being.

Table 11. Test for Correlations of the Key Learning Areas

Key Learning Areas		N	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	Int	Discussion
English	Mathematics	78	.439**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Science		.158	.167	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Mathematics	English	78	.439**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Science		.563**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Science	English	78	.158	.167	Not Significant	Accept
	Mathematics		.563**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 11 shows the correlation analysis between English and Mathematics scores reveals a moderate positive correlation (Pearson's $r = 0.439$, $p < 0.01$), indicating a reliable relationship between the two subjects. As English scores increase, there is a

corresponding increase in Mathematics scores. This suggests that proficiency in English is associated with a positive impact on Mathematics performance. The statistical significance ($p < 0.01$) underlines the robustness of this correlation, emphasizing its practical significance for educators and curriculum planners.

Conversely, the correlation between English and Science scores is weak and not statistically significant (Pearson's $r = 0.158$, $p = 0.167$). Although there is a positive correlation, the lack of significance suggests that any observed relationship may be due to random chance. Caution is advised in drawing conclusions about a direct connection between English and Science performance. Educators may need to explore additional factors influencing this relationship to inform targeted interventions.

In the case of Mathematics and Science, there is a strong positive correlation (Pearson's $r = 0.563$, $p < 0.01$), indicating a reliable and significant relationship between these subjects. Higher scores in Mathematics are associated with higher scores in Science, suggesting that proficiency in one subject positively influences performance in the other. Educators could consider integrated instructional approaches that leverage this strong correlation to enhance overall academic achievement.

In summary, the study reveals a moderate positive correlation between English and Mathematics, a weak positive correlation (though not statistically significant) between English and Science, and a strong positive and significant correlation between Mathematics and Science. These findings provide valuable insights for educators to tailor instructional strategies, emphasizing the interconnectedness of subjects and the potential benefits of integrated teaching approaches.

Hansen, M., & Gonzalez, T. (2014) their study examines the correlation between various classroom activities and academic performance gains in math and science among middle school students in North Carolina. It finds that certain activities, such as listening, taking notes, and using technology in math class, are associated with increased math achievement. Similarly, completing science experiments and projects, as well as listening to teachers explain scientific concepts, are linked to gains in science achievement. These findings suggest that active engagement and hands-on learning in the classroom contribute to improved academic performance in math and science subjects. Overall, the study underscores the importance of pedagogical approaches that foster student engagement and active learning across STEM disciplines.

Part IV. Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Proficiency and Grade 7 Learner's Academic Performance in the Key Learning Areas

<i>Domains</i>	<i>English</i>		<i>Mathematics</i>		<i>Science</i>	
	<i>p</i>	<i>sig-value</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>sig-value</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>sig-value</i>
Communication and Interpersonal Skill	0.005	0.966 Not Significant	- 0.036	0.754 Not Significant	- 0.116	0.311 Not Significant
Organization and Planning	0.199	0.081 Not Significant	0.165	0.15 Not Significant	0.145	0.205 Not Significant
Classroom Management	-0.04	0.725 Not Significant	0.021	0.854 Not Significant	-0.06	0.604 Not Significant
Assessment and Coaching	0.081	0.478 Not Significant	0.14	0.221 Not Significant	0.046	0.689 Not Significant
Collaboration and Teamwork	- 0.151	0.188 Not Significant	-0.07	0.544 Not Significant	- 0.067	0.562 Not Significant
Flexibility and Adaptability	0.088	0.441 Not Significant	0.073	0.527 Not Significant	- 0.013	0.91 Not Significant

The correlation analysis conducted on the proficiency skills of teachers and the learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science revealed several interesting findings. Across all proficiency skills assessed - Communication and Interpersonal Skill, Organization and Planning, Classroom Management, Assessment and Coaching, Collaboration and Teamwork, and Flexibility and Adaptability - the

correlation coefficients with learner's academic performance were not statistically significant.

This implies that there is no strong linear relationship between the proficiency skills of teachers and the learner's academic performance in the subjects of English, Mathematics, and Science. In other words, variations in teachers' proficiency in these skills do not appear to have a significant impact on learner's academic achievements in these specific subjects.

In the study conducted by Hansen, M., & Gonzalez, T. (2014) the findings suggest that factors other than teachers' proficiency skills may play a more influential role in determining learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science. Factors such as learner's individual abilities, home environment, peer interactions, and instructional methods may have a greater impact on academic outcomes in these subjects.

While proficiency in teaching skills is undoubtedly important for effective instruction, this analysis underscores the complexity of factors influencing learner achievement and highlights the need for comprehensive approaches to improving educational outcomes. Further research exploring additional variables and their interactions could provide deeper insights into the dynamics of teacher-learner relationships and academic performance.

Table 13. Results of Test for Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Proficiency in Terms of Communication and Interpersonal Skills and the Grade 7 Learner's Academic Performance in the Key Learning Areas

Survey Questions		Academic Performance in English		Academic Performance in Mathematics		Academic Performance in Science	
			Remarks		Remarks		Remarks
Seeks out and listens to others who have contrary opinions.	Pearson Correlation	- .059	No Linear Relationship	.065	No Linear Relationship	.015	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.607	Not Significant	.574	Not Significant	.897	Not Significant
Makes people comfortable in different situations.	Pearson Correlation	.047	No Linear Relationship	.154	Weak	.060	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.685	Not Significant	.179	Not Significant	.602	Not Significant
Varies communication approach when dealing with others from different background	Pearson Correlation	- .018	No Linear Relationship	- .050	No Linear Relationship	- .113	Negative Weak Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.873	Not Significant	.662	Not Significant	.325	Not Significant
Builds strong interpersonal relationships with other people	Pearson Correlation	- .073	No Linear Relationship	- .101	Negative Weak Relationship	- .062	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.526	Not Significant	.380	Not Significant	.591	Not Significant
Shows genuine sensitivity to the feelings of others.	Pearson Correlation	.004	No Linear Relationship	- .063	No Linear Relationship	- .057	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.974	Not Significant	.581	Not Significant	.623	Not Significant
Informs people of events that are relevant to them.	Pearson Correlation	- .124	Negative Weak Relationship	- .130	Negative Weak Relationship	- .107	Negative Weak Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.280	Not Significant	.257	Not Significant	.349	Not Significant
Makes persuasive, high impact presentations before groups.	Pearson Correlation	.129	Weak	.014	No Linear Relationship	- .064	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.262	Not Significant	.901	Not Significant	.576	Not Significant
Handles questions from the audience well.	Pearson Correlation	.115	Weak	.091	No Linear Relationship	.035	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.315	Not Significant	.430	Not Significant	.759	Not Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 13 shows the analysis of the relationship between teachers' teaching proficiency in terms of communication and interpersonal skills and the learner's academic performance yields complex findings across different subjects.

For the performance in English, there is no linear relationship with any of the assessed teaching proficiency, as indicated by Pearson Correlation values close to zero and p-values greater than 0.05. This suggests that the teachers' communication and interpersonal skills, as evaluated in this study, do not significantly impact the performance of learners in English.

Similarly, in Mathematics, most correlations are not statistically significant, except for a weak positive correlation (Pearson Correlation = 0.154, $p > 0.05$) with the competency of making people comfortable in different situations. This implies that while there is a slight association between this specific teaching competency and Mathematics performance, the overall impact is weak and should be interpreted with caution.

In Science, the results show predominantly no linear relationships, with most Pearson Correlation values close to zero and p-values exceeding 0.05. There is a negative weak correlation (Pearson Correlation = -0.113, $p > 0.05$) between the competency of varying communication approach with others from different backgrounds and Science performance. However, this negative correlation is weak, and the lack of statistical significance suggests limited practical significance.

It suggests that the evaluated communication and interpersonal skills of teachers, as outlined in this study, may not be substantial determinants of learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science. It is crucial to recognize the multifaceted nature of teaching and learning, with various factors influencing academic outcomes. While communication and interpersonal skills are undoubtedly vital aspects of effective teaching, additional variables not covered in this study may contribute significantly to learner's performance in these subjects. Further research and exploration of diverse teaching proficiency and their impact on academic achievement are warranted for a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between teacher skills and learner success.

The research conducted by Mushtaq, I., & Khan, S. N. (2012) focuses on investigating factors that influence college students' performance in intermediate examinations, particularly examining their approach to communication, access to learning facilities, availability of proper guidance, and levels of family stress. These factors are identified as crucial elements shaping students' academic outcomes. Effective communication skills are highlighted as essential, as students who can effectively articulate their thoughts and engage in class discussions tend to have a deeper understanding of course materials, which positively impacts their exam performance. Additionally, access to learning resources such as libraries, laboratories, and study materials is noted as critical for facilitating learning and comprehension. Proper guidance from teachers and mentors is emphasized as important for supporting students' academic journey, providing them with clear instructions, feedback, and mentorship to navigate challenges effectively. Conversely, family stressors such as financial difficulties or personal conflicts are recognized as potential barriers to academic success, as they can

contribute to increased anxiety, distraction, and decreased motivation among students. Addressing these factors comprehensively through support systems, resources, and interventions is essential for promoting students' academic performance and overall well-being.

Table 14. Results of Test for Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Proficiency in Terms of Organization and Planning and the Grade 7 Learner's Academic Performance in the Key Learning Areas

Survey Question		Performance in English		Performance in Mathematics		Performance in Science	
			Remarks		Remarks		Remarks
Monitors information that is relevant to on-going projects and activities	Pearson Correlation	.199	Weak	.165	Weak	.145	Weak
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.081	Not Significant	.149	Not Significant	.205	Not Significant
Obtains and uses relevant information to identify symptoms and underlying problems	Pearson Correlation	-.040	No Linear Relationship	.020	No Linear Relationship	-.059	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.725	Not Significant	.865	Not Significant	.605	Not Significant
Makes decisions on time.	Pearson Correlation	.081	No Linear Relationship	.138	Weak	.047	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.478	Not Significant	.227	Not Significant	.686	Not Significant
Anticipates negative and positive consequences.	Pearson Correlation	-.151	Negative Weak Relationship	-.072	No Linear Relationship	-.066	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.188	Not Significant	.533	Not Significant	.565	Not Significant
Knows when expert knowledge is needed and seeks it out to solve problems	Pearson Correlation	.088	No Linear Relationship	.071	No Linear Relationship	-.013	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.441	Not Significant	.535	Not Significant	.912	Not Significant
Develops plans and schedules to achieve specific goals efficiently.	Pearson Correlation	.099	No Linear Relationship	.008	No Linear Relationship	-.061	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.387	Not Significant	.943	Not Significant	.596	Not Significant
Prioritizes tasks in order to stay focused on those that are most important.	Pearson Correlation	-.010	No Linear Relationship	-.015	No Linear Relationship	-.125	Negative Weak Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.933	Not Significant	.893	Not Significant	.276	Not Significant
Organizes people around specific tasks to help them work together on a common objective	Pearson Correlation	.121	Weak	-.019	No Linear Relationship	-.017	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.293	Not Significant	.872	Not Significant	.886	Not Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 14 presents the Results of Test for Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Proficiency in Terms of Organization and Planning and the Academics Performance of the Learners. The examination of the relationship between a teachers' teaching proficiency in organization and planning and the learner's academic performance yielded interesting insights. Looking at the performance in English, there is a weak positive correlation (Pearson Correlation = 0.199, $p = 0.081$) with the teachers' ability to monitor relevant information for ongoing projects. Although not statistically significant at the 0.05 level, this suggests a potential positive link between the teachers' organizational skills and English performance.

Similarly, in Mathematics, there is a weak positive correlation (Pearson Correlation = 0.165, $p = 0.149$) with the same competency of monitoring relevant information, though it does not reach statistical significance. In Science, the correlation is also weak (Pearson Correlation = 0.145, $p = 0.205$). These findings imply that the teachers' ability to stay informed about ongoing activities may have a modest association with learner performance in Mathematics and Science.

Conversely, there are no significant linear relationships between academic performance and proficiency such as obtaining and using relevant information, making decisions on time, anticipating consequences, seeking expert knowledge, developing plans and schedules, prioritizing tasks, and organizing people around specific tasks. The lack of statistical significance in these cases suggests that these specific organizational and planning proficiency may not strongly influence learner's performance in English, Mathematics, or Science.

In conclusion, the study indicates that the teachers' skill in monitoring relevant information for ongoing projects may have a modest positive correlation with learner performance in English, Mathematics, and Science. However, other organizational and planning proficiency examined in this study do not appear to have significant associations with academic outcomes. Further research may be beneficial to explore additional factors contributing to the complex dynamics between teacher proficiency and learner achievement.

Teacher proficiency significantly impacts learner's performance, encompassing effective classroom management, diverse instructional materials, pedagogical employability, effective communication, and subject content knowledge. Adodo (2019) defines teacher proficiency as a combination of subject content knowledge, pedagogical skills, classroom communication, and competent evaluation of instructional objectives. This competence is crucial for creating a learning environment and promoting positive learner performance. The statement emphasizes the multifaceted nature of teacher proficiency and its direct connection to learner's academic success.

Table 15. Results of Test for Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Proficiency in Terms of Classroom Management and the Grade 7 Learner's Academic Performance in the Key Learning Areas

Survey Questions		Performance in English		Performance in Mathematics		Performance in Science	
			Remarks		Remarks		Remarks
Encourage learners to express their opinion, discuss, and responding related to learning	Pearson Correlation	.077	No Linear Relationship	-.089	No Linear Relationship	.067	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.501	Not Significant	.436	Not Significant	.563	Not Significant
Learning management for learners to work together.	Pearson Correlation	.088	No Linear Relationship	-.065	No Linear Relationship	.102	Weak
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.442	Not Significant	.569	Not Significant	.373	Not Significant
Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups in meaningful exploration	Pearson Correlation	.033	No Linear Relationship	-.053	No Linear Relationship	.018	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.774	Not Significant	.647	Not Significant	.873	Not Significant
Provide activities for learners to learn happily	Pearson Correlation	.126	Weak	.116	Weak	-.028	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.271	Not Significant	.310	Not Significant	.807	Not Significant
Focus on real and lively practice for learners to be able to think and solve the problem	Pearson Correlation	.059	No Linear Relationship	.141	Weak	.072	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.611	Not Significant	.218	Not Significant	.531	Not Significant
Activities are selected by the learners according to their ability and interest	Pearson Correlation	-.165	Negative Weak Relationship	-.015	No Linear Relationship	-.044	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.148	Not Significant	.899	Not Significant	.699	Not Significant
Physical environmental condition for enhancing one's learning by working.	Pearson Correlation	-.099	No Linear Relationship	.092	No Linear Relationship	.033	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.389	Not Significant	.424	Not Significant	.775	Not Significant
Exhibited effective and constructive behavior management skills by applying positive environment	Pearson Correlation	-.140	Negative Weak Relationship	.102	Weak	-.040	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.223	Not Significant	.377	Not Significant	.727	Not Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 15 shows the results of Test for Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Proficiency in Terms of Classroom Management and the Academics Performance of the Learners in English, Mathematics, and Science. Across the assessed

teaching methods, none displayed a significant correlation with academic performance in any subject. Traits like encouraging learners to express opinions, managing classroom structures for exploration, providing enjoyable learning activities, focusing on practical problem-solving, allowing learner-selected activities, creating positive learning environments, and promoting collaborative learning showed correlations close to zero or weak correlations lacking statistical significance across all subjects.

Only the method related to "learning management for learners to work together" exhibited a weak positive correlation with Science, but this correlation was not statistically significant. Similarly, "exhibiting effective behavior management skills through a positive environment" displayed weak correlations in Mathematics and a negative weak correlation in English, yet these weren't statistically significant.

These findings suggest that during this evaluation period, the examined teaching approaches may not directly influence or predict academic achievements in English, Mathematics, or Science. It implies that other unmeasured factors could have a more significant impact on academic success during this timeframe.

One of which is the study conducted by Valiandes (2018) found learners made better progress in classrooms where differentiated instruction methods were systematically employed compared to learners in classrooms where differentiated instruction methods were not: Findings revealed that the quality of differentiated teaching demonstrated by teachers had a great impact on the learner's academic performance when these methods in teaching were integrated into mixed classrooms, thus promotes equity, optimization of quality and effectiveness in teaching.

Table 16. Results of Test for Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Proficiency in Terms of Assessment and Coaching and the Grade 7 Learner's Academic Performance in the Key Learning Areas

Survey Questions		Academic Performance in English		Academic Performance in Mathematics		Academic Performance in Science	
			Remarks		Remarks		Remarks
Establishing a climate conducive to learning—a learning environment based on mutual respect and trust	Pearson Correlation	-.025	No Linear Relationship	-	Negative Weak Relationship	-.026	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.827	Not Significant	.327	Not Significant	.819	Not Significant
Evaluating the learning outcomes and re-diagnosing learning needs—have a sense of progress towards goals	Pearson Correlation	.043	No Linear Relationship	-	No Linear Relationship	.002	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.707	Not Significant	.487	Not Significant	.987	Not Significant
A growing recognition that teacher quality is a critical factor in learner success	Pearson Correlation	.029	No Linear Relationship	-	No Linear Relationship	-.068	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.801	Not Significant	.760	Not Significant	.552	Not Significant
Mentors learners in content and skills difficulties	Pearson Correlation	.179	Weak	-	No Linear Relationship	-.081	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.116	Not Significant	.804	Not Significant	.480	Not Significant
Encourage the learner to complete a task through questions	Pearson Correlation	.174	Weak	-	No Linear Relationship	-.027	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.128	Not Significant	.457	Not Significant	.813	Not Significant
Coach the learner what the goals are	Pearson Correlation	-.118	Negative Weak Relationship	-	Negative Weak Relationship	-.041	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.305	Not Significant	.320	Not Significant	.720	Not Significant
Coach the learner to do an activity in another way	Pearson Correlation	.212	Weak	.027	No Linear Relationship	-.027	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.062	Not Significant	.813	Not Significant	.812	Not Significant
Use mentoring if a learner can independently make a decision	Pearson Correlation	.010	No Linear Relationship	-	Negative Weak Relationship	-.105	Negative Weak Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.934	Not Significant	.102	Not Significant	.360	Not Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 16 shows the relationship between a teachers' teaching proficiency in assessment and coaching and the learner's academic performance provides valuable insights. In terms of establishing a conducive learning environment based on mutual respect and trust, there is no significant linear relationship with performance in English, Mathematics, or Science. This suggests that this specific competency may not strongly influence learner's academic outcomes in these subjects.

Similarly, the teachers' ability to evaluate learning outcomes and re-diagnose learning needs, reflecting a sense of progress towards goals, does not show a significant linear relationship with performance in English, Mathematics, or Science. This indicates that this competency may not be a determining factor in learner's achievements in these subjects.

The recognition of teacher quality as a critical factor in learner success also does not exhibit a significant linear relationship with academic performance in English, Mathematics, or Science. The findings suggest that the general acknowledgment of the importance of teacher quality may not directly translate into improved learner outcomes in these specific subjects.

Mentoring learners in content and skills difficulties, encouraging learners to complete tasks through questions, coaching learners on goals and alternative approaches, and using mentoring when a learner can independently make decisions show weak positive or negative correlations in some cases. However, the lack of statistical significance implies that this proficiency may have limited influence on learner's performance in English, Mathematics, and Science.

In conclusion, the study suggests that, based on the evaluated proficiency in assessment and coaching, there is no strong and consistent linear relationship with learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science. The findings emphasize the need for further exploration and consideration of various factors that contribute to the complex dynamics between teacher proficiency and learner achievement in specific subjects.

In addition, Admiraal et al. (2019) state that assessment is integral to teaching. Teachers use assessment techniques that assess learner's skills (i.e., cognitive, affective, and psychomotor). In his research conducted in Turkish Secondary Schools, the teachers are more successful and use various evaluation techniques to evaluate learner's performance and give more weightage to observation, class performance, and discussion., than weekly or monthly test scores. The key objective of the assessment is to explore the learners learning; it is only possible when the teacher assesses all the aspects of learner's personality (i.e., communication, expression, writing, reading, explaining, and thinking skills.)

Table 17. Results of Test for Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Proficiency in Terms of Collaboration and Teamwork and the Grade 7 Learner's Academic Performance in the Key Learning Areas

Survey Question		Academic Performance in English		Academic Performance in Mathematics		Academic Performance in Science	
			Remarks		Remarks		Remarks
Formulates clear goals that inspire team members' commitment.	Pearson Correlation	.061	No Linear Relationship	-	No Linear Relationship	-	Negative Weak Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.597	Not Significant	.951	Not Significant	.141	Not Significant
Selects team members appropriately, taking into account diversity of viewpoints and technical skills.	Pearson Correlation	.188	Weak	.198	Weak	.153	Weak
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.100	Not Significant	.083	Not Significant	.180	Not Significant
Provides team members with clear vision of what is to be accomplished by the team	Pearson Correlation	.126	Weak	.060	No Linear Relationship	-	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.271	Not Significant	.599	Not Significant	.993	Not Significant
Creates a process for monitoring team performance.	Pearson Correlation	.021	No Linear Relationship	-	No Linear Relationship	.007	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.856	Not Significant	.645	Not Significant	.950	Not Significant
Assigns tasks and responsibilities to individual team members consistent with their proficiency and interest.	Pearson Correlation	.012	No Linear Relationship	-	Negative Weak Relationship	-	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.917	Not Significant	.325	Not Significant	.988	Not Significant
Creates a team setting in which team members feel that their suggestions make a difference	Pearson Correlation	.160	Weak	.068	No Linear Relationship	.030	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.161	Not Significant	.556	Not Significant	.797	Not Significant
Recognizes, praises, and rewards team members for their contributions.	Pearson Correlation	.045	No Linear Relationship	-	No Linear Relationship	.016	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.693	Not Significant	.757	Not Significant	.890	Not Significant
Assists the team in acquiring the resources and support it needs to accomplish its goals.	Pearson Correlation	.019	No Linear Relationship	.144	Weak	.018	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.868	Not Significant	.210	Not Significant	.875	Not Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 17 shows the relationship between a teachers' teaching proficiency in collaboration and teamwork and the learner's academic performance reveals interesting patterns. Examining the performance in English, it appears that the teachers' ability to formulate clear goals that inspire team members' commitment does not show a significant linear relationship. This suggests that this specific competency may not strongly impact learner's academic outcomes in English.

In Mathematics, there is a weak positive correlation (Pearson Correlation = 0.198, $p = 0.083$) between the teachers' competency in selecting team members appropriately, considering diversity of viewpoints and technical skills, and learner performance. Although this correlation is statistically significant at the 0.05 level, the strength of the relationship is considered weak. In Science, a similar weak positive correlation (Pearson Correlation = 0.153, $p = 0.180$) is observed for this competency. These findings imply that the teachers' skill in team selection may have a modest association with learner's performance in Mathematics and Science.

Other proficiency in collaboration and teamwork, such as providing a clear vision, creating a process for monitoring team performance, assigning tasks based on proficiency, creating a setting where suggestions matter, recognizing contributions, and assisting teams in acquiring resources, do not show significant linear relationships with academic performance in English, Mathematics, or Science.

In conclusion, while there are some weak positive correlations in the context of selecting team members appropriately and performance in Mathematics and Science, the overall results suggest that the evaluated proficiency in collaboration and teamwork may not strongly influence learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science. Additional research and consideration of various factors contributing to the dynamics between teacher proficiency and learner achievement are warranted for a comprehensive understanding.

Espinosa (2020) highlights the importance of lesson study as a culture of professional development that promotes teachers working together, sharing experiences, and observing each other during teaching. This collaborative approach enhances teachers' effectiveness in learner achievement. However, the study suggests that there is no strong linear relationship between teachers' proficiency in assessment and coaching and learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science. This suggests that the relationship between teacher proficiency and learner achievement is not straightforward, and other factors may play a role. Overall, collaborative professional development activities like lesson study are valuable and effective, but the relationship between certain aspects of teacher proficiency and learner academic performance is nuanced and not solely determined by one aspect of teacher proficiency. Both call for a more comprehensive understanding of the interplay between teaching practices, assessment methods, coaching strategies, and various contextual factors. A holistic understanding is necessary to enhance learner's academic success.

Table 18. Results of Test for Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Proficiency in Terms of Flexibility and Adaptability and the Grade 7 Learner's Academic Performance Key in the Learning Areas

Survey Question		Academic Performance in English		Academic Performance in Mathematics		Academic Performance in Science	
			Remarks		Remarks		Remarks
Look for positive ways to make changes	Pearson Correlation	-.032	No Linear Relationship	-.085	No Linear Relationship	.022	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.778	Not Significant	.461	Not Significant	.847	Not Significant
Adapt to change and new ways of working quickly	Pearson Correlation	.083	No Linear Relationship	.158	Weak	.066	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.469	Not Significant	.166	Not Significant	.568	Not Significant
Show willingness to learn new methods.	Pearson Correlation	.024	No Linear Relationship	.168	Weak	.009	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.836	Not Significant	.143	Not Significant	.937	Not Significant
Work collaboratively with learners	Pearson Correlation	-.117	Negative Weak Relationship	.054	No Linear Relationship	-.002	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.306	Not Significant	.641	Not Significant	.987	Not Significant
Teachers are facilitators of educational learning environment	Pearson Correlation	.114	Weak	.111	Weak	.060	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.321	Not Significant	.333	Not Significant	.600	Not Significant
Flexible in considering change in plans for improvements.	Pearson Correlation	.229*	Very Strong Positive	.092	No Linear Relationship	.096	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.044	Not Significant	.425	Not Significant	.401	Not Significant
Eliminates the idea of generation gaps	Pearson Correlation	.204	Weak	.165	Weak	.041	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.073	Not Significant	.149	Not Significant	.724	Not Significant
Encourages strong feedback mechanism	Pearson Correlation	.023	No Linear Relationship	.172	Weak	.019	No Linear Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.844	Not Significant	.133	Not Significant	.870	Not Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is

The table 18 shows the relationship between a teachers' teaching proficiency in flexibility and adaptability and the learner's academic performance yields intriguing findings. In terms of looking for positive ways to make changes, adapting to change and new ways of working quickly, and showing a willingness to learn new methods, there is no significant linear relationship with performance in English, Mathematics, or Science. This suggests that this specific proficiency related to flexibility and adaptability may not strongly influence learner's academic outcomes in these subjects.

Interestingly, the teachers' ability to be flexible in considering changes in plans for improvements shows a very strong positive correlation with performance in Mathematics (Pearson Correlation = 0.229, $p = 0.044$). While this correlation is statistically significant at the 0.05 level, it's important to note that the strength of the relationship is considered very strong. However, this competency does not show significant linear relationships with performance in English or Science. This implies that the teachers' flexibility in adjusting plans for improvement may have a notable impact on Mathematics performance specifically.

Other proficiency such as working collaboratively with learners, perceiving teachers as facilitators of the learning environment, eliminating the idea of generation gaps, and encouraging a strong feedback mechanism do not exhibit significant linear relationships with academic performance in English, Mathematics, or Science.

In conclusion, the study suggests that, overall, the evaluated proficiency in flexibility and adaptability may not strongly influence learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science. The exception is the significant positive correlation between the teachers' flexibility in considering changes in plans for improvements and Mathematics performance. Further exploration and consideration of various factors contributing to the dynamics between teacher proficiency and learner achievement are necessary for a comprehensive understanding.

Teacher proficiency, including flexibility, adaptability, and subject matter expertise, plays a crucial role in the teaching-learning process. However, the relationship between teacher proficiency and learner achievement is nuanced and requires further exploration. The first conclusion suggests that evaluated proficiency in flexibility and adaptability may not strongly influence learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science, with the exception of a significant positive correlation between teachers' flexibility and changes in plans for improvements and Mathematics performance.

Jadama (2019), argues that teachers' in-depth knowledge of the subject matter allows them to use various methodologies suited to deliver it, enabling them to confidently select teaching strategies and skills best suited for learner's understanding. The exception in Mathematics performance emphasizes that specific elements of teacher proficiency might have a notable impact on learner achievement.

In conclusion, the connection between teacher proficiency and learner academic performance highlights the multifaceted nature of this relationship and the need for a deeper exploration of the dynamics between teacher proficiency and learner achievement in various subjects.

Part V. Teachers' Continuing Professional Development Plan

The results presented in the previous section have paved way for the development of teacher's continuing professional development plan. The proposed plan is to improve a teacher's skill, knowledge and effectiveness in the classroom. It's all about identifying specific professional goals and objectives that a teacher wants to achieve, identifying the specific areas that needs improvement, developing a roadmap for professional growth, identifying the resources and support required to support to implement the plan effectively, establishing timeline with clear milestone and deadlines for achieving the outline goals. Learners intervention plan is a plan structured to support individuals who may be struggling with their learning. It typically involves identifying specific challenges a learner is facing and developing strategies to address them. The key components of intervention plan often include the goal setting, establishing clear and measurable learning goals that align with the learner's need, implementing targeted intervention and strategies to identified challenges, collaboration involving educators, parents and relevant professionals to work together in supporting the learner and periodically evaluating the effectiveness of the interventions and making changes to the plan if necessary.

Conclusions

The researchers arrived the following conclusion:

1. The level of the teachers' teaching proficiency in terms of Communication and Interpersonal Skills, Organization and Planning, Classroom Management, Assessment and Coaching, Collaboration and Teamwork, and Flexibility and Adaptability were proficient.
2. The level of grade 7 learner's academic performance in the following key learning areas: English, Mathematics; and Science were very satisfactory.
3. There is no significant relationship on the grade 7 learner's academic performance in the key learning areas English, Mathematics; and Science. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.
4. There is no significant relationship between the level of the teachers' teaching proficiency and the grade 7 learners' academic. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.
5. Teachers' continuing professional development plan is developed based on the findings, educators in the district to enhance their teaching competencies and contribute to sustained academic success of their learners. This comprehensive approach to professional development aligns with the goal of continually improving teaching practices to meet the evolving needs of students and educational standards.

Recommendations

According to the study's findings on teachers' teaching proficiency and grade 7 learner's academic performance in the 4th Congressional District of Quezon. The following recommendations are suggested:

- 1.** The study revealed that the teachers surveyed generally exhibit a proficient level of teaching proficiency across various domains, including communication and interpersonal skills, organization and planning, classroom management, assessment and coaching, collaboration and teamwork, and flexibility and adaptability. Teachers should continue to participate in professional development programs to enhance their teaching proficiency, especially in areas where correlations with learner performance are weaker. This can help them continuously improve their skills. Thus, it is recommended to monitor individual learner progress. Implement systems for monitoring individual learner progress to identify and address potential learning gaps early, ensuring that all learners continue to excel.
- 2.** The study revealed that the learner's academic performance in English, Mathematics, and Science is very satisfactory, with grand means falling within this range. This indicates that learners are achieving at a high level in these subject areas, which may be attributed to effective teaching practices and support.
- 3.** The study revealed that the relationship between teachers' teaching proficiency and learner's academic performance reveals varying degrees of correlation in different domains. While some correlations are weak and do not reach statistical significance, there are noteworthy connections, such as the positive impact of organization and planning skills on English performance, and the positive influence of selecting team members appropriately on Mathematics performance. However, these relationships are subject-specific and may require further investigation to understand the underlying factors. Thus, it is recommended to explore subject-specific strategies: Investigate subject-specific teaching strategies that may have a more significant impact on academic performance. Teachers can then adapt their practices accordingly.
- 4.** The study revealed that the teacher development plan is a structured and purposeful approach to improving teacher skills, knowledge, and effectiveness in the classroom. It involves setting specific professional goals, identifying areas for improvement, creating a roadmap for growth, and establishing timelines and resources to support the plan's implementation. On the other hand, the learner's intervention plan is designed to support individuals struggling with their learning. It includes setting clear and measurable learning goals, implementing targeted interventions, fostering collaboration among educators, parents, and professionals, and regularly evaluating the effectiveness of the plan. These plans aim to provide tailored support to help learners overcome challenges and achieve their educational objectives. Thus, it is recommended to encourage the sharing of successful teacher development and intervention strategies among educational institutions to foster innovation and improvement across the education sector.
- 5.** Future researchers should delve deeper into the specific factors and teaching methods that contribute to the positive correlations observed in certain areas. This can provide

valuable insights for instructional improvement. This suggests that these educators possess the necessary skills and competencies to effectively engage with learners in the classroom. Thus, it is recommended to encourage ongoing professional development. The plan should focus on targeted professional development in communication, interpersonal skills, classroom management, assessment techniques, and adaptability. Subject-specific pedagogical training is advised to capitalize on positive correlations between teaching proficiencies and learner performance in specific subjects. Workshops, collaborative learning communities, technology-enhanced instruction, and differentiated teaching methods should be emphasized. Ongoing professional development and support, including mentorship programs, aim to ensure continuous growth and improvement in teaching practices. These recommendations collectively aim to enhance teachers' competencies and contribute to sustained academic success for learners in the district.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher commits to respect the data privacy laws and other rules indicated in the data privacy agreement memorandum from the Department of Education. All contacts will also be established prior to the study's conduct. The health and safety of the stakeholders as respondents will be taken into account by effective contact with the local IATF and adherence to safe health standards. In addition, accurate data interpretation with total impartiality will be maintained in order to enhance the study's standard utilizing the confirmability approach or respondent validation via summary of results if they agree with any of the likely emerging viewpoints. Finally, the researcher is liable for any issues that may occur about the participants, gather data, or the integrity of the study.

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